

Modern Educational Supervision, Teachers' Morale and Competence in Cluster 3 in Calamba City

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the relationship between modern educational supervision and the teachers' morale and competence in Cluster 3 public secondary schools in Calamba City. Specifically, it assessed the manifestation level of modern educational supervision in terms of comprehensiveness, quality management, cooperation and organization, communication, and participation; the level of teachers' morale in terms of work interest, salary, job status, work atmosphere, and human relationships; and the teachers' competence in various domains such as content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, and professional growth. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, data were gathered from school heads and teachers. Statistical tools such as the t-test and Person

were used to determine significant differences and relationships between variables. Findings revealed no significant difference between the assessment of modern supervision and teacher competence, while some aspects of teachers' morale salary, job status, and work atmosphere showed significant variation. Moreover, results indicated a significant positive relationship between the level of modern educational supervision and both teachers' morale and competence. Test of Significant Relationship between the Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads and Level of Teachers' Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City, the r values ranging from .250 to .821 were interpreted as with low positive to high positive correlation as to correlate Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads and Level of Teachers' Competence. The computed probability values .000 to .049 were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result shows that there is significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The study concludes that effective modern supervision enhances teachers' motivation, performance, and overall instructional competence, underscoring the vital role of collaborative and participatory supervision in fostering school improvement. The proposed outcome was the C.A.R.E. Program (Creating Advancement and Reward Equity), which aimed to develop current educational supervision procedures while also improving teachers' morale and competency. It focused on professional development for principals, wellness and recognition programs for teachers, and collaborative supervision practices. Schools can use C.A.R.E. Program to develop a more motivated, competent, and participatory teaching workforce, which may foster continual improvement in educational quality. It also supports teachers by addressing both financial needs and professional growth, ensuring they feel valued and motivated. Salary enhancement initiatives promote fair compensation, while incentive programs such as performance-based bonuses and recognition awards boost morale and encourage excellence. Professional growth support through scholarships, training subsidies, and university partnerships enables career advancement without financial strain. Retention strategies like long-service awards, allowances, and wellness programs further strengthen commitment and loyalty.

Keywords: *Modern Educational Supervision, Teachers' Morale, Teachers' Competence, Supervision Practices, Public Secondary Schools*

INTRODUCTION

Educational supervision encompasses the tasks performed by administrative personnel in the field of education. Supervisors of education make sure the institution runs smoothly and in accordance with the law's regulations. This field's goal is to ensure that instructors are carrying out their duties properly and that students are getting the finest education possible. Education supervision also refers to a comprehensive effort made by school administrators to mentor teachers and other educational staff members for the institution's improvement. It includes both material and human components. The students, parents, instructors, and other staff members, as well as the neighborhood and other state officials, make up the human elements. On the material side, there are playgrounds, buildings, equipment, and money. In addition to them, the curriculum, instructional strategies, and methodologies fall under the purview of supervision.

According to Kashyap (2020), modern educational supervision was based on the idea that teachers, students, parents, and administrators are all partners in a creative and cooperative enterprise called education, and that supervisors serve as their academic leaders by inspiring, advising, and motivating them to improve the educational process. When planning and organizing the educational activities and programs, this may be done efficiently and successfully if there is strong cooperation among them regarding their preferences and personalities. It now refers to educational supervision, which includes programs and activities for guaranteeing student educational advancement as well as teacher professional development and enhancement of the overall teaching and learning process. In this context, it is easy to see how modern supervision involves activities and programs in addition to the more typical classroom visits, making supervision a full endeavor.

The limits of teachers are being reached. The demands made of them appear to be rising dramatically. Their duties are expanding to include acting as front-line social workers in addition to instructing pupils in a particular subject and encouraging a love of study. For a school to function effectively overall, there needs to be high teacher morale. Because of its significance, sustaining the morale of the teaching staff should be a top priority for administrators and educators. When attempting to raise morale, one area that can be addressed is the school's professional culture. In order to boost morale, administrators should also concentrate on issues with accountability and show instructors that they are supported.

Every stakeholder in education is impacted by the problem of low teacher morale (Heick, 2020). When a teacher's morale is poor, they experience stress, dissatisfaction with their work, burnout, and emotional exhaustion (Will, 2021). These instructors carry their work-related stress and tiredness home with them, which has an impact on their personal lives as well. Low morale among instructors makes it difficult for them to perform their duties to the best of their abilities, which lowers the standard of instruction for students. Three factors that have a detrimental impact on teacher morale are the professional culture of a school, worries about teacher responsibility, and a lack of support from school administrators (Bradford & Braaten, 2018). There are numerous ways to address the issues influencing teacher morale. A common vision and set of objectives, as well as a focus on professional development, have a favorable impact on professional culture. Accountability practices that emphasize progress, holding teachers accountable to their colleagues, and an emphasis on professional development can all help with accountability issues. By publicly praising teachers' accomplishments, involving them in decision-making, and exhibiting visible leadership within the school, administrators' support can be increased.

To satisfy modern educational demands and improve their competency in administering assessments, educators must master a variety of educational competencies. This is the norm in the field of education. The competences required a professional judgment that incorporates knowledge, professional responsibility, experience, and student involvement in order to perform the duties of carrying out the classroom assessment (Sajali, 2018). To produce effective classroom assessments in schools, teachers need to have the necessary knowledge, abilities, and attitudes. According to Sh. Siti Haizumah (2019), a teacher's effectiveness is based on how well they can assess and facilitate learning. According to the Ministry of Education of Malaysia (2006), a teacher's qualities include being skilled, competent, qualified, enthusiastic, devoted, and having the soul of an educator. So, it is abundantly evident that in order to implement classroom assessment that is efficient and achieve the stated classroom assessment's goal, teacher competency is crucial.

This study determined the modern educational supervision, the teachers' morale, and competence in public secondary schools in Calamba City. The rationale for conducting this research stemmed from the growing recognition that effective educational supervision played a crucial role in improving instructional quality, sustaining teacher motivation, and enhancing overall school performance. As the educational landscape continued to evolve, school heads were expected to practice modern supervision approaches characterized by collaboration, communication, and participatory leadership to support teachers in meeting the demands of 21st-century learning. Understanding the then-current state of teachers' morale and competence in relation to these supervisory practices was essential to ensure that educators remained motivated, professionally equipped, and aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). By assessing these variables, the study provided valuable insights that guided school leaders, teachers, and educational policymakers in formulating strategies that strengthened teacher development, promoted positive work environments, and ultimately improved the quality of education in Calamba City public secondary schools.

METHODS

The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational design to examine the manifestation of modern educational supervision and its relationship with teachers' morale and competence. The respondents consisted of school heads and teachers who provided assessments of supervision practices and their own levels of morale and competence. The research locale was situated within public secondary schools, where supervision practices and teacher experiences could be observed in their natural context. To gather data, a structured survey questionnaire served as the primary instrument, carefully designed to measure indicators of supervision (comprehensiveness, quality management, cooperation and organization, communication, and participation), morale (work interest, salary, job status, work atmosphere, and human relationships), and competence (content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, and professional growth). The data-gathering procedure involved the systematic distribution and retrieval of questionnaires from the respondents, ensuring reliability and completeness of responses. For the treatment of quantitative data, statistical tools such as the t-test were applied to determine significant differences in perceptions between groups, while Pearson r was utilized to establish correlations among supervision, morale, and competence. Results revealed that while modern supervision and teacher competence did not significantly differ in assessment, certain aspects of morale—particularly salary, job status, and work atmosphere—showed notable variations. Importantly, findings confirmed a significant positive relationship between modern educational supervision and both teachers' morale and competence, underscoring the crucial role of effective supervision in fostering teacher motivation and professional growth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problem Number 1. What is the manifestation level of modern educational supervision of school heads of Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by Teachers and School Head Themselves in terms of Comprehensive, Quality Management, Cooperative and Organization, Communicative, and Participatory?

Table 1.2 *Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads of Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by Teachers and School Head in terms of Quality Management*

Indicators in terms of Quality Management	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
<i>My school head...</i>							
1. Demonstrate reliability and consistency in my leadership role.	3.00	M	3.48	FM	3.24	M	7

2.	Remain open to constructive criticism and suggestions from stakeholders.	4.00	FM	3.53	FM	3.76	FM	1
3.	Act as a leader who inspires and supports rather than merely manages.	3.50	FM	3.45	FM	3.48	FM	4
4.	Ensure that educator appraisals are integrated into the school's management plan.	3.00	M	3.52	FM	3.26	FM	5
5.	Conduct performance appraisals of educators consistently, fairly, and accurately using the approved instrument.	3.00	M	3.44	FM	3.22	M	8
6.	Verify that all submitted documents are accurate, complete, signed, dated, and properly stamped.	3.00	M	3.51	FM	3.25	FM	6
7.	Provide every educator with a copy of the QMS instrument and other relevant documents.	4.00	FM	3.47	FM	3.74	FM	2
8.	Prepare and monitor the implementation of the QMS in the school.	3.50	FM	3.49	FM	3.50	FM	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT		3.38	FM	3.49	FM	3.43	FM	
Standard Deviation						0.514		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Fully Manifested (FM) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Partially Manifested (PM)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Manifested (M) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested (NM)

Quality Management obtained a general assessment mean of 3.43, which was Strongly Agree or Fully Manifested (FM). The indicator “My school head remains open to constructive criticism and suggestions from stakeholders” had the highest composite mean of 3.76 (FM), showing that school heads value inclusivity and feedback in management. On the other hand, “My school head conducts performance appraisals of educators consistently, fairly, and accurately using the approved instrument” had the lowest composite mean of 3.22 (M), interpreted as Agree or Manifested. The standard deviation (SD = 0.514) suggests minimal variation, indicating consistent perceptions among respondents.

The findings imply that quality management practices in schools are generally strong, with school heads demonstrating openness to constructive criticism and suggestions from stakeholders. In real-life situations, this openness can foster a collaborative environment where teachers, parents, and even students feel empowered to share ideas that improve school operations and teaching practices. For instance, when a principal listens to teachers' feedback about classroom challenges, it can lead to practical solutions such as adjusting schedules or providing additional resources, which directly enhances morale and instructional effectiveness. However, the relatively lower rating on performance appraisals suggests that while evaluations are being conducted, there may be concerns about consistency, fairness, or accuracy. In practice, this could mean that some teachers feel their efforts are not fully recognized or that appraisal systems do not always capture the breadth of their contributions. Such perceptions can affect motivation and trust in leadership. The minimal variation in responses indicates that these views are widely shared among educators, reflecting a common experience across the schools surveyed.

Table 1.3 *Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads of Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by Teachers and School Head in terms of Cooperative and Organization*

Indicators in terms of Cooperative and Organization	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
<i>My school head...</i>							
1. Collaborate with teachers to address classroom discipline problems.	3.00	M	3.61	FM	3.30	FM	5
2. Observe classroom instruction and provide feedback to improve teaching strategies.	4.00	FM	3.55	FM	3.77	FM	2
3. Foster cooperation among teachers to develop new and effective teaching practices.	4.00	FM	3.32	FM	3.66	FM	3
4. Encourage teachers to take responsibility for improving their teaching skills.	3.50	FM	3.59	FM	3.54	FM	4
5. Promote a sense of responsibility among teachers for their students' learning outcomes.	4.00	FM	3.58	FM	3.79	FM	1
6. Provide parents or guardians with relevant information on school and student performance.	2.00	M	3.56	FM	2.78	M	8
7. Review school administrative procedures and reports to check for mistakes or errors.	3.00	M	3.52	FM	3.26	FM	7
8. Collaborate with principals from other schools on challenging work tasks.	3.00	M	3.54	FM	3.27	FM	6
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.31	FM	3.53	FM	3.42	FM	
Standard Deviation					0.504		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Fully Manifested (FM) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Partially Manifested (PM)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Manifested (M) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested (NM)

The Cooperative and Organization dimension had a general assessment of 3.42, interpreted as Strongly Agree or Fully Manifested (FM). The indicator “My school head promotes a sense of responsibility among teachers for their students’ learning outcomes” obtained the highest composite mean of 3.79 (FM), while “My school head provides parents or guardians with relevant information on school and student performance” registered the lowest composite mean of 2.78 (M). The standard deviation (SD = 0.504) indicates consistent responses.

It may be concluded that school heads highly demonstrate cooperative and organizational supervision practices, particularly in promoting accountability among teachers and fostering teamwork within the school. The findings imply that cooperative and organizational practices in schools are generally strong, with school heads effectively promoting a sense of responsibility among teachers for their students’ learning outcomes.

This can be observed when principals encourage teachers to take ownership of student progress, such as through regular monitoring of academic performance, collaborative lesson planning, or peer mentoring. Such practices foster accountability and motivate teachers to improve instructional strategies, ultimately benefiting learners. However, the relatively lower rating on providing parents or guardians with relevant information about school and student performance highlights a gap in communication and stakeholder engagement. In practice, this could mean that parents are not consistently updated on their children’s academic standing or school initiatives, which may limit their ability to provide support at home. Strengthening communication channels—such as parent-teacher conferences, newsletters, or digital platforms—would help bridge this gap and enhance collaboration

between schools and families. The consistency of responses, as reflected in the standard deviation, suggests that these perceptions are widely shared among teachers, pointing to a common experience across the schools surveyed.

Table 1.4 *Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads of Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by Teachers and School Head in terms of Communicative*

Indicators in terms of Communicative <i>My school head...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Participate actively in communication about teaching and instructional matters.	4.00	FM	3.62	FM	3.81	FM	1
2. Engage in discussions about everyday school activities and practical issues.	3.50	FM	3.54	FM	3.52	FM	4.5
3. Share and clarify the school's vision, mission, and objectives with stakeholders.	3.00	M	3.52	FM	3.26	FM	7.5
4. Communicate expectations and rules regarding student social behavior.	3.00	M	3.52	FM	3.26	FM	7.5
5. Discuss plans and initiatives related to school development.	3.50	FM	3.54	FM	3.52	FM	4.5
6. Share outcomes and results related to teaching and learning performance.	4.00	FM	3.49	FM	3.74	FM	3
7. Provide concrete and constructive feedback on teachers' work.	3.50	FM	3.53	FM	3.51	FM	6
8. Facilitate communication with stakeholders regarding school improvement plans.	4.00	FM	3.49	FM	3.75	FM	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.56	FM	3.53	FM	3.55	FM	
Standard Deviation					0.504		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Fully Manifested (FM) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Partially Manifested (PM)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Manifested (M) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested (NM)

Communicative supervision recorded a general assessment of 3.55, which is Strongly Agree or Fully Manifested (FM). The indicator “My school head participates actively in communication about teaching and instructional matters” had the highest composite mean of 3.81 (FM), while “My school head shares and clarifies the school’s vision, mission, and objectives with stakeholders” and “My school head communicates expectations and rules regarding student social behavior” both had the lowest composite mean of 3.26 (FM). The standard deviation (SD = 0.504) indicates consistent responses.

It can be inferred that school heads in public secondary schools of Calamba City exhibit strong communication practices, especially in promoting open dialogue regarding teaching and instructional improvement.

The findings imply that communicative supervision in public secondary schools of Calamba City is generally strong, with school heads actively engaging in discussions about teaching and instructional matters. This can be observed when principals regularly meet with teachers to discuss lesson delivery, classroom challenges, and strategies for improving student outcomes. Such open dialogue fosters collaboration, builds trust, and motivates teachers to refine their practices, ultimately enhancing the quality of instruction. However, the relatively lower ratings on clarifying the school’s vision, mission, and objectives, as well as on communicating expectations for student behavior, suggest that while communication is strong in instructional areas, there may be gaps in aligning stakeholders with the broader goals and values of the school. For example, parents and students may not always be

fully aware of the school’s long-term direction or behavioral standards, which can lead to misunderstandings or inconsistent practices. Addressing these gaps through clearer communication—such as regular assemblies, newsletters, or stakeholder meetings—would strengthen the sense of shared purpose and reinforce discipline and accountability. The consistency of responses indicates that these perceptions are widely shared among teachers, reflecting a common experience across schools.

Table 1.5 *Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads of Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by Teachers and School Head Themselves in terms of Participatory*

Indicators in terms of Participatory <i>My school head...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Join teachers in their social events to build rapport and camaraderie.	2.50	M	3.54	FM	3.02	M	7
2. Support teachers during emergency situations or personal difficulties.	3.50	FM	3.49	FM	3.49	FM	2
3. Raise the morale of teachers by recognizing and appreciating their achievements.	4.00	FM	3.55	FM	3.77	FM	1
4. Enhance teachers’ confidence in their professional abilities.	3.00	M	3.48	FM	3.24	M	6
5. Delegate appropriate routine tasks to teachers.	3.00	M	3.51	FM	3.25	FM	5
6. Assign administrative tasks according to teachers’ abilities and interests.	3.00	M	3.53	FM	3.26	FM	4
7. Encourage teachers to express opinions and suggestions that contribute to work improvement and school development.	3.50	FM	3.43	FM	3.46	FM	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.21	M	3.50	FM	3.36	FM	
Standard Deviation					0.543		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Fully Manifested (FM) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Partially Manifested (PM)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Manifested (M) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested (NM)

Participatory supervision earned a general assessment of 3.36, which was Strongly Agree or Fully Manifested (FM). The indicator “My school head raises the morale of teachers by recognizing and appreciating their achievements” achieved the highest composite mean of 3.77 (FM), while “My school head joins teachers in their social events to build rapport and camaraderie” had the lowest composite mean of 3.02 (M). The standard deviation (SD = 0.543) indicates acceptable consistency in responses.

This implies that school heads actively practice participatory supervision, particularly through recognition and morale-boosting initiatives, though they can further improve in social engagement and informal relationship-building with teachers. The findings suggest that while professional recognition among school heads is strong, there is room for improvement in building personal rapport and fostering informal relationships with teachers. Strengthening this area could enhance camaraderie, trust, and teamwork within the school community, creating a more supportive environment. The results indicate acceptable consistency in responses, showing that teachers generally share similar perceptions of their school heads’ supervisory practices. This consistency implies that the issue is systemic rather than isolated, and therefore requires school-wide attention. It highlights that participatory supervision is well-practiced, but school leaders should strive to balance professional recognition with personal

engagement. Doing so would not only improve teacher morale and retention but also contribute to a more cohesive and resilient school culture where collaboration and innovation can thrive.

Problem Number 2. What is the level of teachers’ morale in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers Themselves in terms of Work Interest, Salary, Job Status, Work Atmosphere, and Human relationship?

Table 2.1 *Level of Teachers’ Morale in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Work Interest*

Indicators in terms of Work Interest <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Find joy and satisfaction in performing my teaching duties every day.	4.00	VH	3.46	VH	3.73	VH	2
2. Feel motivated to explore new teaching strategies to improve student learning.	4.00	VH	3.55	VH	3.78	VH	1
3. Look forward to attending school activities and programs.	3.50	VH	3.51	VH	3.50	VH	4
4. Remain committed to accomplishing my tasks even during challenging times.	3.50	VH	3.54	VH	3.52	VH	3
5. Maintain enthusiasm in preparing lessons and instructional materials.	3.50	VH	3.41	VH	3.45	VH	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.70	VH	3.49	VH	3.60	VH	
Standard Deviation					0.846		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Very High (VH) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Low (L)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ High (H) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Very Low (VL)

Work Interest garnered a general assessment of 3.60, which was verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree or Very High (VH). Among the indicators, “I feel motivated to explore new teaching strategies to improve student learning” received the highest composite mean of 3.78 (VH), reflecting teachers’ enthusiasm for innovation and instructional improvement. Conversely, “I maintain enthusiasm in preparing lessons and instructional materials” obtained the lowest composite mean of 3.45 (VH), still indicating a strong sense of engagement. The standard deviation (SD = 0.846) shows moderate variation in responses.

This result implies that teachers in Calamba City public secondary schools demonstrate very high morale and professional dedication, maintaining a positive attitude toward teaching and continuous improvement despite challenges. The findings emphasize that teachers demonstrate a strong sense of work interest, especially when it comes to exploring new teaching strategies and improving student learning. This reflects their natural drive toward innovation and their commitment to enhancing instructional practices. In real-life situations, this can be seen when teachers eagerly attend professional development seminars, experiment with technology in the classroom, or adopt creative approaches to engage students. Their enthusiasm for innovation shows that they are not only open to change but also motivated to continuously improve the learning experience.

However, the findings also reveal that sustaining enthusiasm in routine tasks—such as preparing lessons and instructional materials—remains a challenge. In practice, this is evident when teachers feel energized during workshops or collaborative projects but may experience fatigue or reduced motivation when faced with repetitive tasks like lesson planning, grading, or paperwork. These routine responsibilities, though essential, can sometimes feel burdensome and overshadow the excitement of innovation.

This situation highlights the importance of school leaders providing support systems that balance both aspects of teaching. For example, offering shared lesson banks, digital tools for lesson preparation, or collaborative planning sessions can ease the workload and make routine tasks more engaging. Recognition of teachers' efforts, even in the less glamorous aspects of their work, can also boost morale. In real life, a teacher who feels appreciated not only for their innovative teaching strategies but also for the time they invest in preparing lessons is more likely to sustain high levels of motivation.

The findings suggest that while teachers are naturally inclined toward innovation, their enthusiasm for routine tasks can be strengthened through supportive leadership, resource provision, and collaborative opportunities. In everyday school settings, this balance ensures that both creative and routine aspects of teaching are valued, leading to a more motivated, resilient, and effective teaching workforce.

Table 2.2 Level of Teachers' Morale in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Salary

Indicators in terms of Salary <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Believe my salary fairly compensates my workload and responsibilities.	4.00	VH	2.62	H	3.31	VH	1
2. Feel financially secure and able to meet my basic needs through my salary.	4.00	VH	2.74	H	3.24	H	2
3. Consider my salary adequate for my professional growth and personal development.	3.50	VH	2.35	L	2.93	H	4
4. Am satisfied with the salary adjustments and benefits I receive.	3.50	VH	2.64	H	3.07	H	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.75	VH	2.52	H	3.14	H	
Standard Deviation					0.776		
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Very High (VH)		1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Low (L)					
2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ High (H)		1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Very Low (VL)					

Salary received a general assessment of 3.14, which was interpreted as Agree or High (H). The indicator “I believe my salary fairly compensates my workload and responsibilities” obtained the highest composite mean of 3.31 (VH), while “I consider my salary adequate for my professional growth and personal development” had the lowest composite mean of 2.93 (H). The standard deviation (SD = 0.776) suggests moderate consistency.

If teachers feel their salary is fair for current workload but inadequate for long-term growth, they may remain committed in the short term but could seek opportunities elsewhere for better financial and developmental support. This has implications for teacher retention, as limited financial capacity for growth may lead to turnover or discourage younger educators from staying in the profession.

Since salary alone may not fully support professional growth, schools and education departments could provide scholarships, training subsidies, or career development programs. Such initiatives would help bridge the gap between perceived fairness of workload compensation and the inadequacy in supporting broader professional and personal aspirations. expound the findings and relate it to real life situation. The implications for motivation and retention are critical. Teachers who feel their salary is fair for current workload but inadequate for long-term growth may remain committed in the short term but could eventually seek opportunities elsewhere—such as in private schools, international teaching posts, or non-teaching professions—that offer better financial and developmental support. In real life, this can lead to turnover, especially among younger educators who are more likely to explore alternative career paths if they feel their growth is financially limited.

The findings underscore the need for complementary support systems. Since salary alone may not fully support professional growth, schools and education departments can step in by offering scholarships, training subsidies, or career development programs. For example, a teacher who cannot afford graduate school tuition might benefit from a scholarship program provided by the Department of Education, or a school could sponsor attendance at professional development workshops. These initiatives would help bridge the gap between perceived fairness of workload compensation and the inadequacy in supporting broader professional and personal aspirations, ensuring that teachers remain motivated, valued, and committed to the profession.

Table 2.3 Level of Teachers' Morale in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Job Status

Indicators in terms of Job Status <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Feel proud of my current position in the school.	3.50	VH	3.20	H	3.35	VH	3
2. Believe my job status reflects my skills, experience, and contributions.	3.50	VH	3.03	H	3.26	VH	5
3. See opportunities for promotion and career advancement in my current role.	3.50	VH	3.14	H	3.32	VH	4
4. Feel secure in my employment and future in the teaching profession.	3.50	VH	3.47	VH	3.49	VH	2
5. Am satisfied with the recognition I receive for my job status.	4.00	VH	3.13	H	3.56	VH	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.60	VH	3.19	H	3.40	VH	
Standard Deviation					0.962		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Very High (VH) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Low (L)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ High (H) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Very Low (VL)

Job Status obtained a general assessment mean of 3.40, which was Strongly Agree or Very High (VH). The indicator “I am satisfied with the recognition I receive for my job status” had the highest composite mean of 3.56 (VH), while “I believe my job status reflects my skills, experience, and contributions” received the lowest mean of 3.26 (VH). The standard deviation (SD = 0.962) indicates a slightly wider spread, reflecting differing perceptions among respondents.

It can be concluded that teachers in Calamba City take pride in their professional identity and job stability, contributing significantly to their morale, although perceptions of recognition and advancement opportunities vary slightly. The findings imply that recognition programs are indeed effective in making teachers feel valued, but recognition alone is not enough if job status does not fully reflect their skills, experience, and contributions. In real-life school settings, this situation often arises when teachers receive praise or awards for their dedication yet remain in the same position for years without opportunities for promotion or advancement. For example, a teacher who has completed advanced training or earned a graduate degree may still hold the same title as colleagues with less experience, which can create frustration and a sense that their professional growth is not being acknowledged in tangible ways.

This disconnect highlights the importance of revisiting promotion systems and aligning job titles with qualifications. In practice, schools could establish clearer pathways for career progression, such as recognizing teachers who specialize in curriculum development, mentoring, or research with higher status roles. Doing so would not only validate their expertise but also motivate others to pursue professional growth.

Additionally, creating structured opportunities for advancement—such as leadership tracks, subject coordinator roles, or senior teacher designations—can ensure that recognition is paired with meaningful career

development. In real life, this could mean that a teacher who consistently demonstrates innovation in teaching strategies is promoted to a role where they can mentor peers, thereby reinforcing both recognition and professional identity.

The implication is that recognition programs should be complemented by systems that reflect teachers' evolving skills and contributions. By aligning status with growth, schools can foster a culture where teachers feel both appreciated and professionally fulfilled, leading to stronger motivation, retention, and overall effectiveness in the education system.

Table 2.4 *Level of Teachers' Morale in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Work Atmosphere*

Indicators in terms of Work Atmosphere <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Work in an environment that promotes cooperation and teamwork.	4.00	VH	3.22	H	3.61	VH	2
2. Feel comfortable and stress-free in my workplace.	3.50	VH	3.05	H	3.27	VH	5
3. Have access to adequate facilities and resources to perform my job effectively.	4.00	VH	2.99	H	3.50	VH	3
4. Experience a school environment that values respect and professionalism.	3.50	VH	3.21	H	3.35	VH	4
5. Believe the school climate encourages creativity and productivity.	4.00	VH	3.27	VH	3.64	VH	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.80	VH	3.15	H	3.47	VH	
Standard Deviation					0.819		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Very High (VH) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Low (L)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ High (H) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Very Low (VL)

Work Atmosphere achieved a general assessment of 3.47, interpreted as Strongly Agree or Very High (VH). The indicator "I believe the school climate encourages creativity and productivity" had the highest mean of 3.64 (VH), while "I feel comfortable and stress-free in my workplace" obtained the lowest mean of 3.27 (VH). The standard deviation (SD = 0.819) indicates moderate response variation.

The findings suggest that teachers perceive their work environment as collaborative, respectful, and conducive to professional growth, although minor stress factors may exist in certain schools. This can be seen when teachers are motivated to design engaging lesson plans, integrate technology into their teaching, or collaborate with colleagues on projects that enhance student learning. Such a climate not only boosts teacher performance but also directly benefits students by promoting dynamic and interactive classroom experiences. This could mean that teachers enjoy the freedom to innovate but struggle with heavy workloads, administrative demands, or large class sizes that contribute to workplace stress. For example, a teacher may feel inspired to implement new teaching strategies but also feel overwhelmed by deadlines, paperwork, or the pressure of meeting performance targets. This indicates that while the atmosphere supports professional growth, there is a need to address factors that affect teachers' well-being. This variation may stem from differences in teaching assignments, personal coping mechanisms, or the level of support received from school leaders.

Some teachers may thrive in a dynamic environment, while others may feel burdened by the same demands. This suggests that school leaders should adopt differentiated approaches to support staff, such as wellness programs, stress management initiatives, or flexible workload arrangements, to ensure that all teachers feel comfortable and

valued. Schools are succeeding in creating climates that encourage creativity and productivity, but they must also prioritize teacher well-being by reducing stressors and fostering a more supportive environment.

Table 2.5 *Level of Teachers' Morale in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Human Relationship*

Indicators in terms of Human relationship <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Maintain a positive and respectful relationship with my colleagues.	3.50	VH	3.55	VH	3.53	VH	4
2. Receive support and encouragement from my school head and peers.	4.00	VH	3.32	VH	3.66	VH	1
3. Communicate openly and effectively with the school community.	4.00	VH	3.24	H	3.62	VH	2
4. Feel appreciated and valued by my co-teachers and administrators.	4.00	VH	3.14	H	3.57	VH	3
5. Show empathy, understanding, and cooperation in working with others.	3.50	VH	3.37	VH	3.44	VH	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.80	VH	3.32	VH	3.56	VH	
Standard Deviation					0.875		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Very High (VH) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Low (L)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ High (H) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Very Low (VL)

Human Relationship obtained a general assessment of 3.56, which was *Strongly Agree or Very High (VH)*. The indicator “I receive support and encouragement from my school head and peers” ranked highest with a composite mean of 3.66 (VH), while “I show empathy, understanding, and cooperation in working with others” had the lowest mean of 3.44 (VH). The standard deviation (SD = 0.875) reflects moderate variability.

This implies that teachers enjoy harmonious interpersonal relationships and professional respect, fostering a positive climate that strengthens morale and collaborative practice. This can be seen when school heads provide constructive feedback, recognize teachers' efforts, and peers collaborate willingly—such as sharing teaching resources or offering emotional support during stressful periods. This kind of encouragement strengthens morale, builds trust, and promotes teamwork within the school community. Some teachers may feel highly supported and cooperative, while others may perceive gaps in empathy or encouragement. This variability underscores the need for school leaders to ensure consistency in fostering positive relationships across the entire institution. Strong support systems from school heads and peers contribute significantly to positive human relationships, but schools must also focus on strengthening empathy and cooperation among teachers. The balance could be achieved through initiatives like peer support groups, recognition programs, and professional development sessions on collaboration and communication.

Problem Number 3. What is the level of teachers’ competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers Themselves in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Development, and Personal Growth and Professional Development?

Table 3.1 *Level of Teachers’ Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy*

Indicators in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	3.50	HC	3.73	HC	3.61	HC	4
2. Used a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	4.00	HC	3.66	HC	3.83	HC	1
3. Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	3.50	HC	3.55	HC	3.52	HC	5
4. Displayed proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English to facilitate teaching and learning.	4.00	HC	3.60	HC	3.80	HC	2
5. Applied ICT skills to facilitate teaching and learning.	4.00	HC	3.62	HC	3.81	HC	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.80	HC	3.63	HC	3.72	HC	
Standard Deviation					0.868		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Competent (HC) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Slightly Competent (SC)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Competent (C) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Competent (NC)

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy received a general assessment of 3.72, interpreted as *Strongly Agree or Highly Competent (HC)*. The indicator “I use a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills” obtained the highest mean of 3.83 (HC), while “I apply a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking” had the lowest mean of 3.52 (HC). The standard deviation (SD = 0.868) indicates moderate response variation.

This demonstrates that teachers possess a high level of pedagogical expertise, particularly in literacy and numeracy, and apply various instructional methods to foster student learning effectively. This is evident when teachers employ differentiated instruction, remedial activities, and interactive approaches to ensure students master reading, writing, and mathematics—skills that are essential for success across all subjects. This strength reflects the emphasis schools place on literacy and numeracy as core learning outcomes, and it shows that teachers are effectively meeting these critical educational goals. In practice, this means that while teachers are confident in teaching basic skills, they may be less consistent in fostering higher-order thinking. For example, a teacher may excel at helping students solve math problems or improve reading comprehension but may provide fewer opportunities for learners to engage in inquiry-based projects, problem-solving tasks, or creative expression. This gap suggests that while foundational skills are well-supported, schools need to strengthen pedagogical approaches that encourage students to think critically, question assumptions, and generate innovative ideas—skills that are increasingly important in the 21st century. Teachers are highly competent in strengthening literacy and numeracy, which ensures students acquire essential academic foundations. However, schools must also prioritize training and support to help teachers consistently integrate strategies that develop critical and creative thinking.

Table 3.2 *Level of Teachers' Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Learning Environment*

Indicators in terms of Learning Environment	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
<i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>							
1. Managed classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.	4.00	HC	3.62	HC	3.81	HC	2.5
2. Maintained a learning environment that promotes fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning.	3.50	HC	3.62	HC	3.56	HC	4
3. Managed learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.	4.00	HC	3.61	HC	3.81	HC	2.5
4. Used learner-centered, gender-sensitive strategies that respect learners' diverse backgrounds and needs.	4.00	HC	3.66	HC	3.83	HC	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.88	HC	3.63	HC	3.75	HC	
Standard Deviation							0.860

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Competent (HC) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Slightly Competent (SC)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Competent (C) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Competent (NC)

Learning Environment garnered a general assessment of 3.75, verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree or Highly Competent (HC). The indicator “I use learner-centered, gender-sensitive strategies that respect learners’ diverse backgrounds and needs” yielded the highest mean of 3.83 (HC), while “I maintain a learning environment that promotes fairness, respect, and care” recorded the lowest mean of 3.56 (HC). The standard deviation (SD = 0.860) reflects consistent perceptions.

It may be concluded that teachers are highly competent in creating inclusive, fair, and supportive classroom environments that promote active learning and gender sensitivity. This is evident when teachers design lessons that accommodate different learning styles, respect cultural backgrounds, and ensure gender sensitivity—for example, by using examples that avoid stereotypes, encouraging equal participation among boys and girls, and differentiating instruction to meet varied abilities. Such practices foster inclusivity and help learners feel valued, which in turn enhances engagement and achievement.

This may mean that while teachers strive to create respectful and caring environments, challenges such as classroom discipline, peer conflicts, or resource limitations sometimes hinder consistency. For instance, a teacher may encourage fairness but struggle when large class sizes make it difficult to give equal attention to all students. This suggests that while respect and care are present, schools need to strengthen support systems—such as counseling services, classroom management training, and policies that reinforce fairness—to ensure these values are consistently upheld.

Teachers are highly competent in fostering inclusive, learner-centered environments, but there is a need to further reinforce fairness, respect, and care to ensure holistic development. In real-life school settings, this balance could be achieved through initiatives such as peer mediation programs, values integration in lessons, and recognition of teachers who model fairness and empathy.

Table 3.3 *Level of Teachers' Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers Themselves in terms of Diversity of Learners*

Indicators in terms of Diversity of Learners	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
<i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>							
1. Demonstrated knowledge and understanding of learners' diverse needs in terms of abilities, learning styles, and socio-cultural backgrounds in designing lesson plans.	4.00	HC	3.42	HC	3.71	HC	2
2. Designed, adapted, and implemented teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents.	4.00	HC	3.38	HC	3.69	HC	3
3. Planned and delivered lessons that address learners in difficult circumstances and those from indigenous groups.	4.00	HC	3.56	HC	3.78	HC	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	4.00	HC	3.45	HC	3.73	HC	
Standard Deviation					0.879		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Competent (HC) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Slightly Competent (SC)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Competent (C) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Competent (NC)

Diversity of Learners had a general assessment of 3.73, which was Strongly Agree or Highly Competent (HC). The indicator “I plan and deliver lessons that address learners in difficult circumstances and those from indigenous groups” attained the highest composite mean of 3.78 (HC), while “I design, adapt, and implement strategies responsive to learners with disabilities and giftedness” recorded the lowest mean of 3.69 (HC). The standard deviation (SD = 0.879) indicates consistency.

This implies that teachers display strong inclusivity and adaptability, addressing the diverse educational needs of students from various backgrounds. Teachers are particularly effective in designing lessons that are inclusive of marginalized or disadvantaged learners. This can be seen when teachers adjust their teaching to accommodate students from indigenous communities by integrating culturally relevant materials, respecting traditions, and providing additional support for those facing economic or social challenges. Such practices ensure that learners from vulnerable backgrounds feel included and are given equal opportunities to succeed.

While teachers are capable of addressing diversity, they may find it more challenging to consistently meet the needs of learners with special education requirements or those who are gifted. For example, a teacher may provide differentiated instruction for struggling learners but may lack specialized training or resources to fully support a child with a disability or to extend learning opportunities for gifted students. This gap suggests the need for more professional development, resource provision, and collaboration with specialists to strengthen inclusive education practices.

Teachers are highly competent in planning lessons for learners in difficult circumstances and indigenous groups, but there is a need to further enhance strategies for learners with disabilities and giftedness.

Table 3.4 *Level of Teachers' Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Curriculum and Planning*

Indicators in terms of Curriculum and Planning <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Planned and delivered lessons based on the curriculum and learning needs.	3.50	HC	3.62	HC	3.56	HC	4
2. Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop mastery of learning content.	3.50	HC	3.72	HC	3.61	HC	3
3. Integrated cross-curricular links to enhance the teaching of the lesson.	4.00	HC	3.68	HC	3.84	HC	1
4. Adapted teaching strategies to meet the varying abilities and needs of learners.	4.00	HC	3.65	HC	3.83	HC	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.75	HC	3.67	HC	3.71	HC	
Standard Deviation					0.788		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Competent (HC) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Slightly Competent (SC)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Competent (C) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Competent (NC)

Curriculum and Planning registered a general assessment mean of 3.71, verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree or Highly Competent (HC). The indicator “I integrate cross-curricular links to enhance the teaching of the lesson” obtained the highest mean of 3.84 (HC), while “I plan and deliver lessons based on curriculum and learning needs” recorded the lowest mean of 3.56 (HC). The standard deviation (SD = 0.788) indicates strong consistency.

These findings signify that teachers are well-versed in curriculum integration and strategic lesson planning, ensuring that lessons are aligned with learning standards and learner diversity. This can be seen when a science teacher integrates mathematics into experiments, or when a history lesson incorporates elements of literature and art. Such practices enrich learning by helping students see connections between disciplines, making lessons more meaningful and engaging. This strength reflects teachers' ability to design lessons that go beyond isolated subject matter and instead foster holistic understanding.

Table 3.5 *Level of Teachers' Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers in terms of Assessment and reporting*

Indicators in terms of Assessment and reporting <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Designed, selected, organized, and used diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	4.00	HC	3.64	HC	3.82	HC	3
2. Monitored and evaluated learner progress using appropriate assessment tools and strategies.	4.00	HC	3.57	HC	3.79	HC	4
3. Communicated promptly and clearly to learners, parents, and stakeholders about learner progress.	4.00	HC	3.72	HC	3.86	HC	1.5

4. Used assessment data to inform planning and improve teaching and learning.	4.00	HC	3.72	HC	3.86	HC	1.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	4.00	HC	3.66	HC	3.83	HC	
Standard Deviation					0.823		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Competent (HC) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Slightly Competent (SC)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Competent (C) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Competent (NC)

Assessment and Reporting yielded a general assessment of 3.83, which was Strongly Agree or Highly Competent (HC). The indicators “I communicate promptly and clearly to learners, parents, and stakeholders about learner progress” and “I use assessment data to inform planning and improve teaching and learning” both obtained the highest mean of 3.86 (HC), while “I monitor and evaluate learner progress using appropriate tools” had the lowest mean of 3.79 (HC). The standard deviation (SD = 0.823) reflects stable perceptions.

The results affirm that teachers are highly proficient in using assessments for instructional decisions, reflecting effective feedback mechanisms and accountability in the teaching process. Teachers’ prompt and clear communication during parent-teacher conferences ensures that parents remain well-informed about their child’s progress. For instance, a parent who regularly receives updates on their child’s reading level is better equipped to provide support at home, strengthening the partnership between school and family. Similarly, instructional adjustments based on assessment data demonstrate how teachers respond to learners’ needs. When a teacher identifies that many students struggle with fractions, they revise lesson plans, integrate manipulatives, and conduct remedial sessions, showing how data-driven planning directly enhances learning outcomes.

At the leadership level, the stable perceptions across teachers allow school heads to design professional development programs with confidence. Workshops may be tailored to focus on innovative assessment tools such as digital quizzes or rubrics for project-based learning, thereby addressing the slightly weaker area of monitoring learner progress. Learners also benefit from this culture of assessment and reporting, as timely feedback makes them feel valued and motivated. A student who receives constructive comments on essays can improve more quickly, boosting both confidence and performance.

Table 3.6 Level of Teachers’ Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers Themselves in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Development

Indicators in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Development <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Established learning environments that respond to community contexts.	4.00	HC	3.60	HC	3.80	HC	1
2. Involved parents and the wider school community in the educative process.	4.00	HC	3.57	HC	3.79	HC	2
3. Maintained collaborative relationships with parents, school colleagues, and other stakeholders to support learner development.	3.50	HC	3.64	HC	3.57	HC	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.83	HC	3.60	HC	3.72	HC	
Standard Deviation					0.767		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Competent (HC) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Slightly Competent (SC)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Competent (C) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Competent (NC)

Community Linkages and Professional Development obtained a general assessment mean of 3.72, verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree or Highly Competent (HC). The indicator “I establish learning environments that respond to community contexts” had the highest composite mean of 3.80 (HC), while “I maintain collaborative relationships with parents, colleagues, and other stakeholders” recorded the lowest mean of 3.57 (HC). The standard deviation (SD = 0.767) indicates tight clustering of responses.

This suggests that teachers in Calamba City effectively connect classroom learning with community contexts and maintain strong professional relationships, ensuring learner development through shared responsibility. Teachers demonstrate competence in community-responsive learning by integrating local traditions into classroom activities, such as using community festivals as themes in reading or math lessons. This approach makes learning more meaningful and relevant, as it reflects the socio-cultural context of the learners. However, challenges remain in parent collaboration. While teachers provide updates, some parents may feel less engaged due to limited communication channels or busy schedules. For example, a parent might only hear about their child’s progress during formal meetings rather than through ongoing dialogue, highlighting the need to strengthen collaborative relationships.

Collegial support also shows room for improvement. Teachers may share strategies informally but often lack structured collaboration. For instance, a science teacher may design excellent community-based projects but fail to coordinate with colleagues in other subjects, missing opportunities for interdisciplinary learning. Similarly, stakeholder engagement tends to be episodic. Schools may invite local leaders or professionals to speak to students, but without sustained collaboration, these efforts remain one-off events. Stronger partnerships could lead to continuous programs such as mentorships or community service projects that benefit learners more holistically.

Table 3.7 *Level of Teachers’ Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City as assessed by School Head and Teachers Themselves in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development*

Indicators in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development <i>As a public-school teacher, I...</i>	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Applied personal and professional reflection to improve practice.	4.00	HC	3.59	HC	3.80	HC	1
2. Developed personal and professional goals based on the PPST.	3.50	HC	3.45	HC	3.47	HC	4
3. Shared teaching practices that support other teachers and improve school programs.	3.50	HC	3.50	HC	3.50	HC	3
4. Pursued opportunities for professional development.	4.00	HC	3.50	HC	3.75	HC	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.75	HC	3.51	HC	3.63	HC	
Standard Deviation					0.823		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Competent (HC) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Slightly Competent (SC)
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Competent (C) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Competent (NC)

Personal Growth and Professional Development attained a general assessment of 3.63, which was Strongly Agree or Highly Competent (HC). The indicator “I apply personal and professional reflection to improve practice” had the highest composite mean of 3.80 (HC), while “I develop personal and professional goals based on the PPST” registered the lowest mean of 3.47 (HC). The standard deviation (SD = 0.823) indicates consistent ratings.

This demonstrates that teachers are proactive in self-assessment, reflection, and continuous learning, which enhances instructional quality and professional growth. This could be seen when a teacher notices that a particular lesson did not engage students as expected. Instead of repeating the same approach, the teacher reflects on what

went wrong—perhaps the activity was too abstract—and then modifies the lesson by adding concrete examples or interactive tasks. This reflective cycle ensures that teaching practices evolve to suit learners’ contexts.

This stability is positive, but it also points to the need for systemic support in helping teachers translate reflection into formalized, PPST-based goals. For example, school leaders could organize mentoring sessions where teachers not only reflect on their practice but also map their reflections to PPST indicators, ensuring that professional growth is both personal and standards-driven.

Problem Number 4. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of School Heads and Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City on the manifestation level of modern educational supervision of school heads, level of teachers’ morale, and competence?

Table 4.1 *The Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of School Heads and Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City on Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads*

	Sub-variables	T value	df	Mean difference	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Comprehensive	Equal variances assumed	.062	170	.01306	.165	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	.148	1.148				
Quality Management	Equal variances assumed	-.692	170	-.11365	.531	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	-.900	1.041				
Cooperative and Organization	Equal variances assumed	-1.088	170	-.21971	.059	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	-3.204	1.238				
Communicative	Equal variances assumed	.147	170	.03118	.594	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	.099	1.011				
Participatory	Equal variances assumed	-1.368	170	-.28712	.126	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	-3.664	1.191				

Level of significance 0.05

The Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of School Heads and Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City on Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads as shown in table 4.1 had generated computed probability values .165, .531, .059, .594, and .126 which were greater than the level of significance of 0.05 using Independent Samples T-test; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the responses of the two groups of respondents on the above-mentioned variables.

This means that the both school heads and teachers share the same perceptions regarding the implementation of modern educational supervision. This implies that school heads and teachers are on the same page when it comes to supervisory practices such as instructional monitoring, feedback, and support for professional growth. For example, if a school head introduces a new supervision strategy—like classroom walkthroughs or peer coaching—teachers are likely to perceive it in the same way as the school heads themselves, reducing the risk of miscommunication or resistance. This shared perspective fosters smoother collaboration, as both groups recognize the value of supervision in improving teaching and learning.

Moreover, the absence of significant differences highlights a culture of coherence within schools. Teachers and school heads may both acknowledge that supervision is not about fault-finding but about guiding instructional improvement. In practice, this could be seen when a school head provides constructive feedback after an observation, and teachers accept it positively because they view supervision as supportive rather than punitive.

For policy and leadership implications, the findings suggest that professional development programs can be designed uniformly for both groups, since their perceptions are aligned. For instance, workshops on modern supervision techniques or data-driven instructional planning can be conducted jointly, promoting shared understanding and collective responsibility. This alignment also strengthens trust and collaboration, ensuring that supervision becomes a tool for growth rather than a source of division.

Table 4.2 *The Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of School Heads and Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City on Level of Teachers' Morale*

	Sub-variables	T value	df	Mean difference	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Work Interest	Equal variances assumed	.381	170	.20706	.228	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	1.785	1.809				
Salary	Equal variances assumed	2.464	170	1.22941	.009	Significant	Reject H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	22.780	169.0				
Job Status	Equal variances assumed	.653	170	.40706	.029	Significant	Reject H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	6.037	169.0				
Work Atmosphere	Equal variances assumed	1.210	170	.65294	.045	Significant	Reject H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	11.191	169.0				
Human Relationship	Equal variances assumed	.822	170	.47647	.262	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	2.273	1.206				

Level of significance 0.05

Meanwhile, as shown in Table 4.2 (Teachers' Morale), the sub-variables Salary (.009), Job Status (.029), and Work Atmosphere (.045) showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$). This implies that school heads and teachers differ in their views regarding these aspects, while Work Interest (.228) and Human Relationship (.262) were not significant, suggesting aligned perceptions in these areas.

It can be concluded that school heads tend to rate teachers' morale higher than the teachers themselves, particularly concerning compensation and workplace environment. This divergence can be seen when school heads believe that salary levels are fair compared to national standards, while teachers may feel that their pay does not match the workload or rising cost of living. Similarly, job status differences may arise when administrators view teaching positions as stable, but teachers may feel insecure due to contractual arrangements or limited opportunities for promotion. Work atmosphere also highlights contrasting experiences: school heads may see the environment as supportive, while teachers may experience stress from large class sizes, administrative tasks, or limited resources.

On the contrary, the alignment in work interest suggests that both school heads and teachers recognize a shared passion for teaching and commitment to learners. For example, teachers remain motivated to innovate in their lessons, and school heads acknowledge this dedication. Likewise, the agreement on human relationships reflects positive collegiality and collaboration. In practice, this could be seen in teachers and school heads working together during school events, mentoring programs, or collaborative planning sessions, where mutual respect and teamwork are evident.

Table 4.3 *The Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of School Heads and Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City on Level of Teachers' Competence*

Sub-variables		T value	df	Mean difference	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Equal variances assumed	.286	170	.16941	.264	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	2.643	169.0				
Learning Environment	Equal variances assumed	.407	170	.24412	.333	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	1.733	1.610				
Diversity of Learners	Equal variances assumed	.936	170	.54782	.165	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	8.653	169.0				
Curriculum and Planning	Equal variances assumed	.151	170	.08235	.562	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	.321	1.115				
Assessment and Reporting	Equal variances assumed	.605	170	.33971	.266	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	5.591	169.0				
Community Linkages and Professional Development	Equal variances assumed	.450	170	.23124	.404	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	1.328	1.124				
Personal Growth and Professional Development	Equal variances assumed	.429	170	.23971	.117	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Equal variances not assumed	3.969	169.0				

Level of significance 0.05

For Table 4.3 (Teachers' Competence), all computed p-values (.117–.562) were greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between the assessments of school heads and teachers.

This means both groups share a common understanding and perception of teachers' competence, suggesting alignment in how teaching skills, instructional practices, and professional abilities are recognized and valued within the school system.

This finding reflects a strong sense of coherence between leadership and teaching staff. For example, when a teacher demonstrates effective classroom management or innovative teaching strategies, both the school head and fellow teachers acknowledge these competencies similarly. This shared perspective reduces the likelihood of conflict or misunderstanding about performance expectations and fosters a supportive environment.

Such alignment also benefits professional development planning. Since school heads and teachers agree on competence levels, training programs can be designed with confidence that they address real needs rather than perceived gaps. For instance, if both groups recognize that teachers are competent in lesson delivery but need more support in integrating technology, professional development can be tailored accordingly.

It can be concluded that both groups have congruent views on the competence of teachers across all domains. Administrators can help maintain teacher morale by recognizing their expertise and involving them in policy and practice decisions. Additionally, principals may improve teacher morale by proactively supporting them.

Principals who are effective serve as custodians of teachers' instructional time, "assist teachers with student discipline matters, enable teachers to develop discipline codes, and promote teachers' authority to enforce policy." Although teachers can take steps to maintain their professional satisfaction and morale on their own, others in the school environment must also nurture, support, and value them. When instructors are given the tools they need to maintain inspiration and zeal in the classroom, both students and teachers will benefit. (Govindarajan, 2021)

As stated by Jones, Lane, and Penny (n.d.) the data were organized based on important factors that corresponded to the research question. Participants described their perceptions of morale during their interactions with various aspects of the guardianship procedure. Numerous participants reported that various aspects of the conservatorship procedure had a negative impact on their morale. The majority of respondents indicated that the loss of authority, voice, and opinions negatively affected their morale. During the process of conservatorship, a

number of educators reported experiencing a decline in morale. Furthermore, teachers reported that their perceptions of the conservatorship process were discouraging, prompting them to seek employment in other schools and school districts.

Problem Number 5. Is there any significant relationship between modern educational supervision and teachers' morale in public schools in Calamba City?

Table 5 Test of Significant Relationship between the Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads and Level of Teachers' Morale in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City

Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads	Level of Teachers' Morale	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Comprehensive	Work Interest	.791	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Salary	.785	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Job Status	.654	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Work Atmosphere	.805	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Human relationship	.619	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Quality Management	Work Interest	.732	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Salary	.525	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Job Status	.590	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Work Atmosphere	.506	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Human relationship	.524	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Cooperative and Organization	Work Interest	.397	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Salary	.357	.002	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Job Status	.278	.020	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Work Atmosphere	.576	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Human relationship	.575	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Communicative	Work Interest	.426	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Salary	.332	.005	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Job Status	.681	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Work Atmosphere	.403	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Human relationship	.342	.007	Significant	Reject H ₀
Participatory	Work Interest	.429	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Salary	.468	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Job Status	.522	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Work Atmosphere	.454	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Human relationship	.647	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

Correlational at the level 0.01

Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

Table 5 shows the Test of Significant Relationship between the Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads and Level of Teachers' Morale in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City, the r values ranging from .278 to .805 were interpreted as with low positive to high positive correlation as to correlate Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads and Level of Teachers' Morale. The computed probability values .000, .002, .005, .007, .020 were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result shows that there is significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

It can be concluded that when school heads engage in supportive, collaborative, and developmental supervision—such as providing constructive feedback, mentoring, and recognizing teachers' efforts—teachers feel more valued and motivated. For example, a teacher who receives regular, encouraging feedback from a school head

after classroom observations is more likely to feel confident and enthusiastic about improving instructional practices. Similarly, when supervision emphasizes professional growth rather than fault-finding, teachers experience reduced stress and greater job satisfaction, which translates into higher morale.

This relationship also manifests in the school climate. A school head who practices modern supervision by fostering open communication, encouraging innovation, and involving teachers in decision-making creates a positive work atmosphere. Teachers in such environments are more likely to collaborate, share best practices, and remain committed to their roles. On the contrary, if supervision is rigid, authoritarian, or inconsistent, morale may decline, leading to disengagement or burnout.

Problem Number 6. Is there any significant association between modern educational supervision and teachers' competence?

Table 6 Test of Significant Relationship between the Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads and Level of Teachers' Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City

Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads	Level of Teachers' Competence	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Comprehensive	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.659	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Learning Environment	.443	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Diversity of Learners	.399	.002	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Curriculum and Planning	.705	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assessment and Reporting	.666	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Community Linkages and Professional Development	.459	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Quality Management	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.481	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.632	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Learning Environment	.618	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Diversity of Learners	.317	.005	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Curriculum and Planning	.485	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assessment and Reporting	.680	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Cooperative and Organization	Community Linkages and Professional Development	.659	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.443	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.399	.002	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Learning Environment	.705	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Diversity of Learners	.821	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Curriculum and Planning	.699	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Communicative	Assessment and Reporting	.593	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Community Linkages and Professional Development	.598	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.612	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.560	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Learning Environment	.780	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Diversity of Learners	.401	.025	Significant	Reject H ₀
Curriculum and Planning	.319	.047	Significant	Reject H ₀	
Assessment and Reporting	.384	.033	Significant	Reject H ₀	

Participatory	Community Linkages and Professional Development	.365	.043	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.661	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.579	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Learning Environment	.532	.002	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Diversity of Learners	.688	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Curriculum and Planning	.585	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Assessment and Reporting	.250	.049	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Community Linkages and Professional Development	.436	.014	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	.507	.004	Significant	Reject H ₀
Correlational at the level 0.01		Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)			

Table 6 shows the Test of Significant Relationship between the Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads and Level of Teachers' Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City, the r values ranging from .250 to .821 were interpreted as with low positive to high positive correlation as to correlate Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads and Level of Teachers' Competence. The computed probability values .000 to .049 were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result shows that there is significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

It can be concluded that the Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads have significant relationship with Level of Teachers' Competence in Public Secondary Schools in Calamba City. The higher the Manifestation Level of Modern Educational Supervision of School Heads, the higher the Level of Teachers' Competence.

This implies that when school heads provide effective supervision—such as mentoring, coaching, and constructive feedback—teachers are more likely to enhance their instructional skills and professional abilities. For example, a teacher who receives guidance on integrating technology into lessons from a school head may develop stronger digital teaching strategies, thereby improving classroom delivery. Similarly, when supervision emphasizes professional growth through classroom observations followed by supportive dialogue, teachers refine their methods, leading to better student engagement and learning outcomes.

The relationship also highlights the importance of supervision in sustaining competence across the teaching workforce. A school head who models modern supervisory practices, such as collaborative planning and data-driven decision-making, encourages teachers to adopt similar approaches. In practice, this could be seen when a school head facilitates peer learning sessions where teachers share best practices, resulting in improved competence across subject areas.

For leadership and policy implications, the findings suggest that investing in modern supervisory training for school heads can yield direct benefits in teacher competence. Structured programs on instructional coaching, differentiated supervision, and reflective practice can equip school heads to better support teachers. This, in turn, ensures that competence is not only maintained but continuously developed, aligning with broader goals of educational improvement.

Proposed Output

The proposed outcome is the C.A.R.E. Program: Creating Advancement and Reward Equity, which aims to develop current educational supervision procedures while also improving teachers' morale and competency. It focuses on professional development for principals, wellness and recognition programs for teachers, and collaborative supervision practices. Schools use CARE Program to develop a more motivated, competent, and participatory teaching workforce, which fosters continual improvement in educational quality.

C.A.R.E. Program: Creating Advancement and Reward Equity

Key Areas	Objectives	Strategies / Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source Of Fund	Success Indicators
Maintain enthusiasm in preparing lessons and instructional materials	Strengthen teacher motivation and creativity in lesson preparation	- Create a display board where students, parents, post-it notes, and certificates highlighting teacher impact	Whole year round	- Principal, Teachers	- No Funds Needed	100% accomplished
		- Kudos cards- distribute blank cards for the school community and students to write words of gratitude, and hand them during assemblies		Principal, Teachers, PTA, Students	School funds	100% accomplished
		- Interest Mapping- create a mind map with the lesson topic in the center. Branch out to connect to popular culture, sports, technology, or local events that students care about.		Principal, Teachers	No funds needed	100% accomplished
Consider my salary adequate for my professional growth and personal development	Enhance perception of compensation as supportive of growth	- Wellness Benefits- frame health and wellness as part of the compensation package. Example: Paid membership to mental health counselling services. The teacher may regain energy to continue growing and learning from students.	Whole year round	School Heads, Budget Officer, Teachers	School Funds	100% accomplished
Believe my job status reflects my skills, experience, and contributions	Promote recognition and merit-based advancement	- Invite alumni or students to create a lasting tribute to a teachers made a difference. This could be a garden spot, book collection, short documentary, or published collection of stories.	Whole year round	Teachers, School Head, Alumni	Alumni Funds	100% accomplished
Feel comfortable and stress-free in my workplace	Improve workplace climate and well-being	- Strengths Mapping. Intend to focus on what teachers or administrators do wrong or need to improve using the Clifton Strengths Assessment. The process is for everyone to share their top 3 strengths or talents, and use them in forming a team. So, leverage what teachers or administrators can do rather than assigning tasks	Whole year round	Teachers, School Heads, Non-Teaching Personnel, Students	School Funds	100% accomplished

Show empathy, understanding, and cooperation in working with others	Strengthen collaboration and interpersonal relationships	Appreciation Chain- Sit or stand in a circle. One person starts by turning to someone next to them and saying, "I appreciate you because... that person turns to the next and does the same. This creates a literal and figurative chain of positivity and expressing gratitude habit.	Whole year round	Teachers, School Heads, Non-Teaching Personnel	School Funds	100% accomplished
Apply a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills	Enhance instructional practices for higher-order thinking	- Compare and Contrast Matrix. The teacher must give the students two or more complex items, theories, historical events, or characters. Instead of using a Venn diagram, use a matrix where they identify specific criteria and analyze how each item performs or fits within those criteria. Ask "In what ways are they different and why do those differences matter?"	Whole year round	Teachers, School Head, Students	No funds needed	100% accomplished
Maintain a learning environment that promotes fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning	Foster an inclusive and respectful classroom culture	- Co-Created Classroom Constitution. Instead of presenting a list of rules, facilitate discussion where students define what respect, safety, and fairness look like and feel. Ask: "How do we want to be treated when we make a mistake? Write the agreement down, have students high with the teacher. Refer back when issues arise.	Whole year	Teachers, School Heads	No funds needed	100% accomplished
Design, adapt, and implement teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents	Strengthen inclusive education practices	- Universal Design Checklist. Make a checklist that asks: a. visual, auditory, tactile- how will students receive information? b. writing, speaking, building, drawing- how will students demonstrate understanding? c. choice, relevance, collaboration- how will students optimize the learning path?	Whole year round	Teachers, School Head, Guidance Counselor	School funds	100% accomplished
Plan and deliver lessons based on the curriculum and learning needs	Ensure curriculum alignment and learner-centered delivery	Identify gaps where content is based on real-world relevance to the students. Adjust scope and sequence to prioritize skills and application	Whole year round	Teachers, Students	No funds needed	100% accomplished
Monitor and evaluate learner progress using appropriate assessment tools and strategies	Improve assessment literacy and learner monitoring	Align assessment to literacy, not just reading speed or accuracy, but a combination of decoding, comprehension, vocabulary, fluency, and critical thinking. Every assessment must be based on the curriculum standard.	Whole year round	Teachers, Learners, School Head	School funds	100% accomplished
Maintain collaborative relationships with parents, school colleagues, and other stakeholders to	Strengthen school-community partnerships	Services learning initiatives where students use their skills to serve the community. Example: Students create informational brochures or posters on health and safety using their writing and design skills to conduct literacy tutorials for younger children in the Barangay.	Whole year round	Teachers, Parents, School Heads, Students, IT Teachers	School funds, PTA funds	100% accomplished

support learner development	Develop personal and professional goals based on the PPST	Support continuous professional development	Educators Growing Together. Designed to align in order to build competent, reflective, and collaborative educators who include teachers and administrators to equip them in delivering learner-centered community engagement and context-relevant	Whole year round	Teachers, School Heads,	School funds	100% accomplished
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CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, several important conclusions were drawn. The school heads of public secondary schools in Calamba City were found to comprehensively demonstrate modern educational supervision practices, particularly in ensuring quality management, fostering cooperation and communication, and encouraging participatory decision-making among teachers. The consistently high composite means across all dimensions indicate that modern supervision is fully manifested and effectively applied in school management operations. Likewise, teachers in these schools generally exhibit very high morale, especially in terms of work interest, human relationships, and work atmosphere, reflecting their commitment, motivation, and professional engagement in their duties. However, the moderate rating in salary highlights compensation as an area that requires improvement to further strengthen teacher satisfaction and retention. In terms of competence, teachers were shown to be highly proficient across all domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), including pedagogy, classroom management, curriculum planning, assessment, and professional development, thereby upholding the standards of effective teaching performance. Furthermore, the study revealed no significant difference between the assessments of school heads and teachers regarding modern educational supervision and teacher competence, suggesting shared perceptions and mutual understanding of school leadership and instructional performance. Nonetheless, significant differences were observed in certain aspects of teachers' morale, particularly salary, job status, and work atmosphere, indicating slight variations in perspectives between teachers and administrators. Finally, the study confirmed a significant and positive relationship between modern educational supervision and both teachers' morale and competence, implying that effective supervisory practices directly contribute to higher teacher motivation, satisfaction, and professional capability. This underscores the vital role of modern educational supervision in enhancing teaching quality and overall school performance.

Recommendation

Based on the findings summarized and the conclusions drawn, several recommendations are hereby offered. Learners are encouraged to actively participate in school and classroom activities that foster collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking, as guided by competent and well-supervised teachers. They should also maximize opportunities provided by their teachers and school heads, such as mentoring programs, remedial sessions, and student leadership activities, to further improve their academic performance and holistic development. Teachers, on the other hand, may continue enhancing their professional competence by attending relevant trainings, seminars, and workshops aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). They are likewise encouraged to strengthen collaboration and collegiality through sharing best practices and mentoring colleagues, while maintaining open communication with school heads to address morale-related concerns such as workload balance and recognition of efforts. Furthermore, teachers may innovate instructional practices that sustain learner engagement and inclusivity in the classroom.

School heads are advised to sustain and further improve modern educational supervision practices by providing structured professional development programs and regular performance feedback sessions. They should also enhance participatory decision-making by involving teachers in planning, policy-making, and evaluation activities, ensuring that their voices are valued. In addition, recognizing and rewarding teacher accomplishments

can boost morale and foster a supportive work atmosphere, while strengthening communication and organizational management to maintain a cohesive and productive school environment.

At the policy level, the Department of Education may continue developing and supporting programs that enhance modern educational supervision competencies among school leaders, such as leadership coaching, mentoring, and capacity-building initiatives. It is also recommended that DepEd review and address compensation-related concerns to uplift teacher morale and job satisfaction. Moreover, institutionalizing monitoring systems will help ensure consistency in the implementation of effective supervisory practices and alignment of teacher development programs with national educational goals.

Future researchers may explore mediating factors between educational supervision and teacher morale or competence, such as leadership styles, school culture, and resource availability. They may also expand the study to other divisions or educational levels to compare results and validate the relationships found in this research. Additionally, qualitative approaches could be employed to gain deeper insights into teachers' lived experiences and perceptions regarding supervision and morale, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Finally, school heads may utilize the Supervisory Enhancement and Teacher Empowerment Program (SETEP) to further strengthen supervisory practices and empower teachers in their professional growth.

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